

Electrochemical Way of Functioning of Cadmium(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Methylpiperazine at DME

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The nitrogen-containing bases have been found to be most suitable complex-forming agents for cadmium(II) and nickel(II)¹. The reduction of the complex compounds of these metals at DME has been studied to calculate stability constants^{2,3}. These complexing agents are important mainly because they are specific and selective. Among the most important organic complexing agents and electrolyte are pyridinium chloride⁴, EDTA with sodium chloride⁵, triethanolamine⁶, glycine⁷, monoethanolamine⁸, isoniazide⁹, 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol¹⁰ and isonicotinic acid hydrazide¹¹. In most of the cases mixed electrolytes and maximum suppressor are used. Thus, sensitivity and accuracy in the measurement of diffusion current tend to decrease. With *N*-methylpiperazine, there is, however, no need of an auxiliary electrolyte and maximum suppressor. Many metals are not reduced under these conditions, thus the sensitivity of the method is increased. This prompted the authors to conduct the present investigation. The method has been utilised for the determination of nickel(II) in alloys.

Results and Discussion

General procedure for the determination of Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}: A calibration graph was prepared for each of the metals by recording the polarograms of the metal at various concentrations in a 0.1M *N*-methylpiperazine at pH 6.5 ± 0.1. The i_d values obtained from the polarograms were plotted against the concentration of metal ions. The polarogram of the solution containing the metal in unknown concentration was then recorded under identical conditions. The i_d values obtained from this wave were referred to the calibration graph for determining concentration of metal ion could then be determined (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM AND NICKEL WITH *N*-METHYLPIPERAZINE SYSTEMS

[*N*-Methylpiperazine] = 0.1M, [Cd^{II} or Ni^{II}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³M, pH = 6.5, $n = 2$, KNO₃ = 0.1 M

Metal	Amount of the metal (mg)		Error %
	Taken	Found*	
Cd	3.37	3.30	-2.08
	5.62	5.70	+1.42
	7.87	7.78	-1.42
	10.12	10.23	+1.08
Ni	1.76	1.80	+2.28
	2.93	2.88	-1.71
	4.10	4.04	-1.47
	5.27	5.19	-1.52

*Average of five replicate analysis.

Effect of *N*-methylpiperazine concentration: The shape of wave does not change when the concentration of *N*-methylpiperazine is increased from 0.1 to 0.5 M. The formation of the complex is evident as the half-wave potential becomes more negative with increasing concentration of the ligand. The various criteria for reversibility and irreversibility¹² indicate that the electrode reactions are reversible for cadmium and irreversible for nickel at the DME.

Effect of metal ion concentration: Polarograms over the concentration upto 6.00 mM were recorded in the presence of 0.1M *N*-methylpiperazine at pH 6.5 ± 0.1. The value of the diffusion current constant (I) was calculated using the Ilkovic equation, $I = i_d/cn^{2/3}t^{1/6}$, and was found to be 3.59 μA for Cd^{II} and 2.50 μA for Ni^{II}. These values were constant upto 6.0 mM concentration for both the metals.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of various anions and metal ions (at 1mM concentration of Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}) with 0.1M *N*-methylpiperazine has been ascertained. The effects of acetate, nitrate, salicylate, citrate, thiosulphate, tartrate and formate ions on the polarograms of the metals were studied. In all cases, the $E_{1/2}$ values remained constant. Ti^{IV}, W^{VI}, Sc^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Al^{III} and alkaline earth metals such as Ba^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ca^{II} did not undergo reduction, and were tolerated in a ten-fold excess. U^{VI}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} underwent reduction at low potentials and were tolerated upto three- to five-fold excess. Only Fe^{III} in the case of Ni^{II} interfered. Interference by Fe^{III} was masked by 10% triethanolamine solution (5 ml).

Mixed polarogram of cadmium and nickel : From the individual polarogram of cadmium and nickel it is apparent that it is possible to differentiate between the two metals when they are complexed with *N*-methylpiperazine as their $E_{1/2}$ values differ by 0.3 V. The results (Tables 2 and 3) obtained are accurate and reproducible.

Analysis of alloys : A sample (0.1–0.5 g) of the alloy was dissolved in concentrated HCl (50–60 ml) and concentrated HNO₃ (10–20 ml). Then 30% H₂O₂ (3–5 ml) was added and the solution was heated on a hot plate until the sample dissolved. After cooling, distilled water (10 ml) was added to dilute the solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate diluted to 50 ml. An aliquot of this solution was taken and the metals determined (Table 4) by the procedure described. Interference by Fe^{III} in the analysis of aluminium alloy and stainless steel alloy was masked by addition of 10% triethanolamine solution (5 ml).

TABLE 2 – SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM AND NICKEL IN A SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

[*N*-Methylpiperazine] = 0.1M, pH = 6.5

Metal taken (mg)		Metal found* (mg)		Error (%)	
Cd	Ni	Cd	Ni	Cd	Ni
2.81	1.47	2.85	1.44	+1.43	-2.04
3.93	2.05	3.87	2.01	-1.53	-1.95
5.06	2.64	5.00	2.68	-1.19	+1.52

*Average of five replicate determinations.

TABLE 3 – DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Ca = 8.02, Cr = 10.4, Mn = 21.16, Ni = 5.86, K = 54.56%

Ni taken mg	Ni found* mg
2.93	2.88 (2.86–2.90)
3.52	3.64 (3.63–3.68)
4.69	4.62 (4.60–4.66)

* Average of five replicate determinations.
Range is given in parenthesis.

TABLE 4 – ANALYSIS OF ALUMINIUM ALLOY AND STAINLESS STEEL FOR NICKEL

Alloy	Composition %	Amount of Ni* (mg)		Error %
		Taken	Found	
Aluminium alloy	Si : 11.250	3.07	3.04	+0.88
	Cu : 01.175			
	Ni : 01.025			
	Mg : 01.120			
	Fe : 00.560 ^a			
	Ca : 00.002			
	Al : 84.926			
Stainless steel	Ni : 09.680	4.84	4.88	+1.24
	Cr : 18.000			
	Fe : 70.710 ^a			

*Average of five replicate analysis.

^aAfter masking with 5 ml of 10% triethanolamine.

Experimental

Polarograms of the deaerated solutions were recorded at 298 K with a Toshniwal polarograph and the pH was measured with a Century pH meter. A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. Oxygen was removed by passing a stream of nitrogen through the test solution. The dropping mercury had the following characteristics : $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.9 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 20.5 \text{ cm}$ in 0.1M KNO₃ solution.

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NOTE

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